

Small, Medium Scale Enterprises and its Impact in the Nigeria Economy Development Within 1998 To 2023

Godwin Eshorame Gali

A Gradxs Scholar enrolled in Ph.D in International Economics Program
With LIUTEBM University, Lusaka, Zambia
goddygali2013@gmail.com

Received: Mar 28, 2025

Accepted: Apr 28, 2025

Published: Apr 30, 2025

Abstract

This paper examines the Gross Domestic Products, annual total financial value of Small and Medium scale Enterprises (SMEs), the annual employment rate as well as the annual infrastructural development in Nigeria as documented by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) and the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) within 1998 to 2023 to assess the Impact of Small and Medium scale Enterprises (SMEs) on the growth and development of the economy of Nigeria. To also highlight the various ways, the government and other stakeholders can help improve SMEs in order for it to be competitive, through the improvement of the country's GDP, employment rate, exchange rate, foreign trade etc.

The main objective of the study is to uncover the impact of SMEs in the economic growth and development in Nigeria from 1998 to 2023.

Quantitative research technique method was used on the secondary data collection from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) annual reports, Nigerian Bureau of Statistics (NBS) reports within the time series of 1998 to 2023 and the regression analysis was applied to analyse the secondary data collected during the period of this study.

It was discovered from the study that intervention of the government such as implementation of the right policies and intervention and provision of essential and adequate infrastructural facilities. Therefore, the key recommendations after due reviews and consideration include improving access to finance through the specialized government schemes, implementation of adequate policies and interventions that will enhance growth of SMEs, encouraging innovation through the adoption of technological facilities and enhancing government policies to create a more favorable and conducive business environment.

Keywords:

Small and medium scale Enterprises (SMEs), Gross Domestic Product(GDP), Development Financial Institution (DFI), economic development in Nigeria, infrastructural development

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Small and medium-scale enterprises (SMEs) has been considered as part of the economy tools for development of countries, and has been under discussion for a long time now. These businesses are being operated with different level of assets, revenues, sizes of employees, depending on the country or sector and it has no standard definition, but however, Small and medium-scale enterprise constitution differs from one country to another and from one industry to another. The Central Bank of Nigeria defined SMEs as businesses with an asset base between ₦5 million and ₦500 million and

staffing levels ranging from 5 to 100 employees. Generally, SMEs constitute over 80% of the nation's business from Agriculture, manufacturing and services. Small, Medium scale Enterprises (SMEs) are responsible for about 90% of employment generation in the country. (Amoah, S. K., & Amoah, A. K. (2018). However, they also assist in infrastructural development and technological development in some developed and developing countries such as Singapore and Nigeria respectively. Financing SMEs is a major catalyst and important factor for the development, growth and sustenance of any economy. Several studies have shown that small and medium scale enterprises act as catalyst for growth and development of a national economy (Chinweuba & Sunday, 2015). This sector has its own fair share of challenges from the scourge of poor and unstable government policy implementation, poor managerial skills of entrepreneur, poor financial state of SMEs, high percentage of unskilled workers engaged and low or epileptic power supply and all these factors and many others impacts on the level of SMEs in the Nigerian economy. It has also been gathered that about only 5% of the SMEs survive after one year in Nigeria, (Okpara, J. O. (2011). Small and medium-scale enterprises operate across various sectors, including manufacturing, services, agriculture, technology, and retail therefore its performance is important to the country's economic development and it contributes about 47% of the country GDP. (Tekola, H., & Gidey, Y. 2019).

However, some countries have been able to transform their SMEs sub-sector to such a vibrant one that they have been able to reduce to the barest minimum their unemployment and poverty level because of the immense contribution of the SMEs sub-sector to the economic growth and development of countries as US, UK, Germany, South Korea which have been able to account for their industrial employment rate to 65% unlike Nigerian whose industrial employment rate is less than 30%. Due to this development so many scholars such as Aremu and Adeyemi (2011); Cravo, Gourly and Becker (2009); Kaigama, Talib, and Ashari (2016); Nagaya (2017) and Taiwo, Ayode and Yusuf (2012) among many others have researched into the relationship between SMEs and economic growth in order to proffer possible solutions and have come up with different and conflicting results which has resulted to further investigation. In furtherance to this, it is observed that majority of the studies applied primary data in the case, while few others use secondary data with time series quantitative research methodology. Therefore, the present study plans to undertake an anatomy of the relationship between SMEs activities and its impact on economic growth and development using dataset for Nigeria from 1998 to 2023. The study goes beyond the existing studies in two ways: firstly, it has applied more recent time series data and secondly, it considers wide specification and robust econometric techniques. On this basis, it provides fresh insight to the existing literature on the relationship between SMEs and economic growth and development in Nigeria.

The research would come up with a set of recommendations for various stakeholders including governments at all levels, SME promoters, Agencies and Departments of Governments involved in the SME sub-sector, Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs), Multilateral Agencies, Banks, Financiers, Investors, etc,

1.1 BACKGROUND STUDY OF SMEs

Small, Medium scale Enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria has been operational before the coming of our colonial masters when our fore-fathers were merchants and craft-men. Although this sector of the economic have never contributed significantly even when it takes care of majority of the population economically. This is due to the country's challenges which lies from poor financing of the sector, poor infrastructural facilities available for utilisation by the sector, lack of education of majority of the entrepreneur, lack of managerial skills and poor organisational skills of the entrepreneur (Rose Ackerman (2005). The developed country after discovering the importance of SMEs have been able

to make out time to organise them well in order to carry out their functions and meet their targeted obligation and objectives.

During the colonial days in Nigeria the colonial master also discovered the importance of the small and medium scale enterprise after the formation of the two tiers of government in the country (i.e. federal and state or regional) before 1957, when states were first created the colonial masters were involved in the financing of this vital sector of the economy since 1960. (Akeredolu-Ale, 1975). After the independence of the country in 1960 the country went further with the implementation several policies in the bid to develop small and medium scale sub-sector such as the introduction of intervention effort and the promulgation of government regulations for the protection of the small scale and medium scale industries. We were also made to understand from an empirical report that an estimate of about 70% of the industrial employment is held by SMEs and more than 50% of the Gross Domestic Product is SMEs generated (T.J. Odeyemi, 2003).

Some of the regulations include Nigeria Enterprises Promotion Act No. 3 of 1977, Patent Right and Design Act No 60 of 1979, the Customs Duties (dumped and subsidized goods) Act No. 9 of 1959, the Industrial Promotions Act No. 40 of 1979, the Industrial Development Tax Act No. 2 of 1971, among others. (Alawe, 2004). Apart from the promulgated Acts by the government to support SMEs other favourable investment policies, institutional and fiscal policies, protective business law and financial incentives were also introduced to encourage the national development and indigenization policy which the small and medium scale are very central. Several micro lending institutions were also established to enhance the capacity and development of small and medium scale enterprises. Such micro credit institutions include Nigeria Bank for commerce and industry (NBCI), National Economic Reconstruction Funds (NERF), People`s Bank of Nigeria (PBN), Community Bank (CB), National Export and Import Bank (NEIB) and the liberalization of the banking sector to enhance the financial institutions for effective participation in the growth and capacity building of small and medium scale enterprises. (K.K. Ogujiuba; et. al 2004).

The Government also established Raw Material Research Institute (RMRI) in 2001 the research report of this institution is useful to SMEs and business organization in their product choice decision, product development delivery strategies to increase SMEs business effectiveness and efficiency, since majority of the SMEs cannot finance research departments on their own, so the consult this institute for possible solutions concerning research and development.

1.2 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

To Study the impact of Small, Medium Scale Enterprises on the increase in Gross Domestic Product of Nigeria economic, as well as to evaluate the level of relationship or the trend of the dependent variable (GDP) and the independent variables (export, unemployment level, commercial bank loan to small, medium enterprises, per capital income and electricity distribution as infrastructure from government)

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW OF SMEs

Despite all these innovations by the government, SMEs businesses still suffer so much challenges and as such so many scholars have done several research studies such as Ming-Wen (2010), that applied dataset covering thirty-seven countries which include developed and developing countries to examine the contribution of SMEs businesses to economic growth of the said countries between 1960 and 1990. The findings reveal that SMEs businesses contribute positively towards economic prosperity of the countries. it was also observed from the study that, in pursuance of economic growth, SMEs in the developed countries generally help in the promotion of entrepreneurship activities, whilst in the developing countries they contribute in terms of job creation to the people.

Dollar, Hallward-Driemeier and Mengistae (2005) examined how infrastructure, access to external finance and frequency of yearly visits by relevant government agencies affect productivity, wages, profits and growth rates of outputs of SMEs firms in Bangladesh, China, Ethiopia and Pakistan. This study was carried out analysing secondary data from World bank annual report and found that infrastructure is the most important factor in explaining performance and, by extension, relevance of the SMEs in these countries. Thus, they concluded that adequate infrastructure enhances productivity, higher returns, and higher economic growth rates.

Anthony and Arthur (2008) investigates the role of micro, small, and medium enterprises in the growth of per capita income in the United States. They used primary method of quantitative analysis on dataset of some manufacturing companies and with regression analysis discovered there was little and no relationship between that SMEs sub-sector and growth in US economy growth.

Aremu and Adeyemi (2011) examines the role of SMEs in fostering economic growth and employment in Nigeria. The researchers employed qualitative approach in conducting the research analysing secondary data on SMEs' data gathered from other research work, CBN and world bank annual reports. They contributed that SMEs are vital agent in creating job opportunities and reducing poverty Kadir (2012) researched on the contributions of small and medium scale enterprises (SMEs) to employment generation in Nigeria, he applied regression analysis on secondary dataset collected at random and concluded that SMEs influence on employment generation is a factor of the level of finance enjoyed by the sector. It could be positive if financing is good and negative for poor financing.

Afolabi (2013) examined the effect of SMEs financing on economic growth in Nigeria between 1980 and 2010. This was a regression analysis research work on a secondary dataset for 30 years and he with the result that financing SMEs is significant to the economic growth in Nigeria considering GDP with respect to wholesale and retail trading business.

Chinweuba and Sunday (2015) evaluated the relationship between SMEs and economic growth of Nigeria. Their findings uncovered through quantitative research that SMEs activities are effective through the expansion of its output and other various means of survival such as financing, provision of infrastructures, training of workforce etc.

Nagaya (2017) studies the impact of SMEs on economic growth using primary dataset for some India firms and uncovered that SMEs activities are growth enhancing through poverty reduction, employment generation, skills development and many others.

Oluwarotimi and Adamu (2017) examined financial institutions financing to SMEs regarding social, economic performance, and economic growth in Nigeria (from 1992 and 2015). The data collected were analysed using regression analysis; the result showed a negative and significant connection between the variables.

Aminu et al (2018) used time series data ranging from 1986 to 2016 to examine the impact of SMEs on Nigeria's economic growth. The study's demonstrated that SMEs in Nigeria contribute favorably to the development of the Nigerian economy by showing a positive and substantial association between production growth and small and medium-scale Enterprises.

Due to the complicated operational nature of SMEs in the world, several researchers have conducted research on the SMEs and related topics, despite that there has not been a clear method of classification for this sector as most countries have their ways of classification base on the workforce

and the annual turnover of the business, for instance in USA enterprises with annual turnover of US\$5m and workforce of 300 – 500 are considered small and medium scale enterprises, in Britain annual turnover of £2m and 200 workforce, in Japan the annual turnover is 100m Japan yen and 250 – 300 workers, while in Nigeria the annual turnover is N6,000,000 and workforce of 10 – 20. However, this sector keeps taking turn for the better as the country's economic policies improve just like the developed countries like USA, North Korea etc.

2.1 CHARACTERISTICS OF SMEs IN NIGERIA

The features of Nigeria's SMEs are same as those of developing countries, which are partly associated to ownership structure, or base, this revolves around the entrepreneur abilities or the main owner or family operating the business. Hence, the owner of the SMEs is either sole proprietorships or partnerships. Even where the registration status is thus that of a limited liability company, the true ownership structure is that of a one-man, family or partnership business. Other common features of Nigeria's SMEs include the following among others.

1. Labour-intensive production processes:

This is a situation where there are more ability that is human and force than the use of machines. Small and Medium scale Enterprises (SMEs) always employ a lot of workforce, because of the believe that it is cheaper to acquire and maintain. (Dundon, T., & Wilkinson, A. 2018). However, this may not be correct, as it is one of the SMEs managerial fallacy, considering the long run effect of keeping humans, it is more expensive to maintain more workers, since every human has different character, which results to higher labour turnover and a disadvantage to the sub-sector. (Henry O. 2007) Therefore, labour-intensive is more expensive on the long-term bases.

2. Concentration of management on the key man:

One of the features of SMEs is their dependence on an individual solely for the running or control of the establishment, as such it operates a centralised managerial system of operation, which means all knowledge comes from a single source and any challenge that cannot be handled by that individual automatically become the downfall of the establishment. (Nisha R. et al (2023). The death of that individual may result to the death of the business, where there isn't any capable individual to take control of the business.

3. Limited access to long-term funds:

The financing of SMEs is always limited, since it is managed and owned by an individual and the downfall of the individual operating the business most time can be the downfall of the business. Therefore, sourcing and accessing funds is always very difficult because of the fear of the financiers as they are aware that the enterprise is owned by an individual and its resources are limited to the owner's funds in the event of any financial challenge as most times they lack collateral. (Dije U.W. 2017). Therefore, the financiers try as much as possible to reduce the business risk by only providing short term funds, even when entails having several cycles for ease of control and recovery.

4. High cost of funds because of high interest rates and bank charges:

The Financing of SMEs is always considered an individual owns a highly risky investment by financiers considering that it, as such they tie such investment risk to higher interest rates and charges to compensate for the trouble involved in taking such risk. (Steve, A. & Paddy, C. (2024). Also SMEs sub-sector are always faced with short term loans from banks, financial houses in order to minimise risk with time, since from experience it has been noticed that SMEs has high mortality rate. Most SMEs survival rate is 5% and they easily fail within the first 3 years of operation due to factors such as poor or inexperience management, poor infrastructure, poor or unstable government policy etc

5. Over-dependence on imported raw materials and spare parts causes high cost:

SMEs that are involved in manufacturing only source few of their raw materials locally and most of the machines they use are imported as such depend strongly on imported raw materials for processing of their finished products. (Mba O.A. and Cletus I.E. (2014). The imported machineries need maintenance and the spare parts for maintenance of the machines are imported as well. Since the skills of management of the SMEs is limited they can't source raw materials locally neither can they fabricate locally the spares use in the machines so they depend more on importation rather than improvise. So SMEs operators depend more on imported raw materials and machineries spare parts. And due to the limited finance they have SMEs only import the items required and the required quantities without considering the advantage of economic of scale which can also be enjoyed through inter-sectoral and intra-sectoral relationship with suppliers and distributors as such may lead to poor integration or co-ordination, higher production costs and poor competitive prices or quality standard to enable competition with other foreign or international company's products.

6. Poor managerial skills due to their inability to pay for skilled labour:

SMEs operating under one-man business has limited resources so, often operate under tight budgets and as such do not have the enough financial capacity to hire experienced professionals or skilled workers who demand higher wages, so they opt for cheaper, less experienced employees or even handle critical tasks themselves without employing adequately experts on the field in order to reduce cost of production, which will affect innovation due to over-utilisation, causing frustration and at the end labour turnover because of lesser compensation. All these also affect the production quality as well as output of the business.

7. Absence of Research and Development and other dept.

SMEs suffer limited resources and finance, and also lack skilled employee as such the enterprise cannot afford many departments such as research and development department, technology adoption, marketing, and expansion creating career development opportunities to attract and retain top talent because of the cost so they maintain department that are only very important for the enterprise to achieve its major objective. Most often SMEs depend on personal experience or conventional ways in solving problems encountered during production or processes. The inability to seize growth opportunities through liquidity buffers or secure external funding with aid of collateral or equity stakes to compensate for the perceived risk associated with undercapitalized businesses

8. Poor documentations of policy, strategy, financials, plans, info, systems:

Most SME owners and managers in Nigeria may lack how to create and maintain effective documentation systems, since they may lack the necessary skill related to record keeping, data management etc, or are aware of the potential benefits in improved organisational efficiency as well as better risk management strategies, as such not fully appreciate the importance of proper formal documentation in business operations, so they opt instead for informal or verbal means which in the long run challenge future growth of the enterprise in accessing credit, establishing credibility with suppliers, customers and investors. Therefore, most SMEs in Nigeria often operate with limited financial and human resources due to lack of necessary funds to invest in robust document management system or hire professionals to handle documentation and various regulatory requirements including tax obligation, licensing and reporting standards. (Mba O.A. and Cletus I.E. (2014)

9. Low entrepreneurial skills, inadequate educational or technical background:

Entrepreneurship involves not only starting a business but also effectively managing it, identifying opportunities, managing risks, and adapting to changes in the market. Most SMEs owners and managers in Nigeria lack sufficient entrepreneurial or technical skills such as strong educational background in specialised areas for instance business management, finance, marketing, e-commerce etc. Without strong entrepreneurial skills, SMEs struggle to operate, innovate, compete, and grow. They may lack the knowledge and creativity to develop new products or services, create comprehensive business plans, leading to efficient resource allocation, ability to manage their finances effectively, effective networking knowledge causing perfect marketing insights to bring about mutual benefits through collaborative effort, ineffective marketing strategies, and realistic growth projections. (Philomena I.I. 2024)

10. Lack of adequate financial record keeping

SMEs work with limited finance as such owners may lack the ability to hire specialist to keep records adequately as required, which enable making good decision easy and faster. The company's financial documentation and record is very paramount to assess profitability, identify areas for cost savings, or area of allocation of resources effectively to enable financial expansion of business in order to encourage financial institution investment and potential business partner's investment. However, poor recording keeping makes it difficult for SMEs to identify areas associated with financial fraud and disallow allow compliance with legal and tax regulations due to the lack of adequate financial record.

11. Lack of distinction of entity and succession plan:

Most SMEs that are managed by a single individual or family are always faced with the problem of entity distinction especially with respect to finances because they often suffer from limited resources and finance, therefore, separation of individual's capital from business capital is a big challenge which creates tax compliance issues as well as regulatory agencies problems due to poor documentation due to lack of technical expertise. The level of combination of personal interest to business interest can also affect the continuity of the business, since major of decisions will be to the interest of the owner rather than the interest of the business, resulting to the death of the business as soon as the owner seize existence. The lack of proper differentiation of personal expenses and business expense can increase risk of non-compliance with tax regulations and also place the business in conflicting position in terms of decision making, and overall organizational stability or survival, through the diminishing value of business growth potential and may affect the future of the business.

2.2 ROLES OF SMALL, MEDIUM SCALE ENTERPRISES IN NIGERIA ECONOMY

Small, Medium scale Enterprises (SMEs) is a very important engine in the economic growth and development of any country. The importance of these businesses cannot be overemphasised they cover almost every facet of a country's growth and development economically and socially starting from employment generation for individuals and corporate, diversification of the economy through industrialisation, export of locally produced goods and agricultural produce. Small and medium scale Enterprises serve as tools of entrepreneurship, economic diversification, and inclusive development. Some of the roles played by SMEs in economic growth and development are thus:

1. Job Creation and Employment development:

SMEs are the greatest employer of labour ranging from youths, women and men, since it is labour-intensive mostly in developing economy like Nigeria. They help in engaging both skilled and unskilled persons, since the large corporations mostly engage skill and formal labour. SMEs engages

all classes of labour. They also provide all kinds of jobs for both youth and women and also help to empower women economically and socially as it covers all sectors such as agricultural sector, manufacturing, retail and services. (Duflo, E. 2012).

2. Contribution to Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of Nigeria

SMEs are responsible for large percentage of the economic activities in a country, since they engage a lot of workers, their product output is also enormous due to the help of diversification of the economy that reduces pressure on one or few sectors for the production of goods such as oil and gas to other sectors like agriculture, manufacturing, services etc.

They also encourage innovation and entrepreneurship for other form of services or products creating room for competition and economic development.

3. Industrialisation, Structural Reformation and value addition:

SMEs encourages industrialisation through local manufacturing, the production of essential goods and services, construction materials, agricultural produce, intermediate or semi-finished products which serves as raw materials, components for large manufacturing companies. SMEs also help in adding value to raw agricultural products, crops to processed goods, which has more value and a wider market appeal. Thereby contributing to economic in a refines and more acceptable form.

4. Innovation and Technology development:

Innovation and technology advancement is essential for long term economic growth. SMEs allow innovation and adoption of technology growth in developing countries which in turn permit increase productivity, improve service delivery through e-commerce, mobile app, digital or electronic payment system in sectors like retail marketing, education, health care delivery etc. However, some of the SMEs engage in innovation through small scale research and development initiatives which benefit the local economy, such as improved agricultural practices or efficient manufacturing processes. The continuous promotion of innovation, new ideas and products from SMEs promotes economic growth. (Yahaya, H. D., Geidam, M. M., & Usman, M. U. (2016).

5. Exports and Foreign Exchange Earning Facilitation:

SMEs often focus on developing local products that can be marketed both locally and abroad. This includes unique handicrafts, manufactured goods, processed foods, agricultural produce, traditional textiles. These products help to expand the country's footprint globally through export and in turn increase the country earning of foreign exchange and also attract foreign investments and partnerships to the country, which makes the country grow and develop economically.

6. Creation of local and Regional Development

SMEs enhance development in the rural area areas where they are located, since they help in the development of rural areas by carrying out social responsibilities through the building of boreholes for water supply, providing rural power supply such as solar light, rural electrification, construction of houses for their employees, creation of road network as well as providing Jobs for people etc thereby populating the rural area and discouraging rural to urban migration and in turn decentralising the urban areas, which result in the decentralization of economic activity and ensures that different regions benefit from the economic wealth generated and reducing income inequality. (Yahaya, H. D., Geidam, M. M., & Usman, M. U. (2016).

7. Promotion of Sustainable Practices

Since SMEs are labour-intensive firms and are major player in circular economic model practices as well as eco-friendly model operator that encourage the renewable energy, recycling waste, repair or recycle of products in order to minimized waste during production, as such they adopt green

technologies, sustainable production methods, and environmentally friendly products and services, which contribute to the broader goal of improved environmental health of the country while contributing to a sustainable economic development country.

2.3 GOVERNMENT SUPPORT OF SMEs IN NIGERIA

Small, Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs) are important to Nigeria's economy, as they contribute significantly to employment, innovation, and economic diversification. However, they face a lot of challenges such as limited access to finance, poor infrastructure, high operational costs, and insufficient technical skills. The government, recognizing the importance of SMEs to the nation's economic building, so implemented various support programs and policies to address these challenges and promote the growth of SMEs.

The following are the types of government support made available for SMEs in Nigeria, stating the initiatives, policies, and programs designed to help these enterprises survive.

Financial Assistance and Credit facilities

One of the major challenge of SMEs in Nigeria is financing, this is because most of small business owners do not have all it takes to qualify for financial institution loan and facility such as collateral, so in order to address this issue, the Nigerian government has introduced several initiatives to improve access to finance for SMEs

Bank of Industry (BoI): The Bank of Industry is a key financial institution that provides loans and financial assistance to SMEs in Nigeria. Bank of Industry was established in 1959 with objectives such as both long-term loans and working capital financing to businesses in various sectors, including agriculture, manufacturing, and services. The bank also provides funding at favourable interest rates to encourage the growth of SMEs.

Nigerian Export-Import Bank (NEXIM): NEXIM offers financing solutions for SMEs involved in export activities. Nigerian Export-Import Bank was established by Act 38 of 1991 as an Export Credit Agency (ECA) with a share capital of N50, 000,000,000 (Fifty Billion Naira) held equally by the Federal Ministry of Finance Incorporated and the Central Bank of Nigeria, with objectives of providing trade finance and export credit guarantees for small businesses. NEXIM helps SMEs access international markets, thus promoting export growth and foreign exchange earnings.

Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises Development Fund (MSMEDF): The Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) launched the MSMEDF on August 15th 2013 to provide financial support to micro, small, and medium-sized businesses. The fund is designed to enhance access to low-interest loans for SMEs in all sectors, including agriculture, manufacturing, and services. The MSMEDF targets businesses with a minimum of N5 million and provides loans with lower interest rates to encourage growth.

Government Subsidized Credit Schemes: The Nigerian government has introduced various credit schemes to provide SMEs with financial support. These include programs like the SME Credit Guarantee Scheme was launched by CBN in 2010 and it guarantees loans for SMEs, the Graduate Employment Loan Scheme (GELS) initiated by the National Directorate of Employment (NDE) was also launched in 1986 to provide labour intensive job for youths in order to reduce unemployment in the country. Lately, the Federal Government of Nigeria (FGN) introduced the Small, Medium Industries Equity Investment Scheme (SMIES) for Banker's Committee was initiated in August 2001 requiring all licensed banks in the country to set aside 10% of their Profit Before Tax (PBT) for equity investment in promotion of SME's, in furtherance to this according to Sanusi (2004), a breakdown of the SMIEIS fund investment by sectoral distribution shows that 68.82% went to the

real sector while service related investment accounted for 31.18%. (Terungwa, A. (2011). The creation of the Small Industries Credit Fund (SICF) by Fed Govt which was formally launched as the Small Scale Industries Credit Scheme (SSICS) in the third National Development Plan was between 1975- 1980. The scheme objective was solely to provide credit to the SMEs and was managed by the States' Ministries of Industry, Trade and Co-operatives and the Credit Enhancement Fund, which is designed to reduce the risks associated with lending to small businesses.

National Economic Reconstruction Fund (NERFUND)

The Federal Government in 1990 set up the National Economic Reconstruction Fund (NERFUND) and became effective 9th January, 1990 with the CBN as one of the facilitating institutions. It was aimed at providing soft and medium finances and long-term loans (5-10 years), to SMEs at concessionary rates of interest in order to help them grow. It was later merged with two development financial institutions to form Bank of Industry.

Capacity Building and Skill Development

One of the key barrier to the growth of SMEs in Nigeria is the limited technical and managerial skills among entrepreneurs and their employees. To address this, the government has set-up various capacity-building programs aimed at enhancing the skill sets of SMEs and their workforce. Some of the skill acquisition centres set-up by the government are vocational centres, technical schools under the National Directorate of Employment (NDE) programme. SMEs Skills development centres, college of technology etc, they are purely funded by government to help train individuals on various technical skills that are required in the manufacturing sector and also perform advisory services to help entrepreneurs enhance their business management skills, financial literacy, and access to markets. The Small, Medium Enterprises Development Centres (SMEDC) also helps business owners develop business plans and improve their operational efficiency. The Federal Government of Nigeria established the National Enterprise Development Programme (NEDEP) in 2013. Part of NEDEP functions is to provide Entrepreneurship training and skills acquisition (Osunde, 2016). The program helps business owners develop technical, managerial, and financial skills to run their enterprises successfully.

Infrastructure Development

There is a lot of challenges cause by lack of adequate infrastructure in Nigeria, all this deter the growth of SMEs in Nigeria for example epileptic electricity supply, poor roads network, and inadequate transportation systems, high the cost of doing business all these result to inefficiency of SMEs. To address these challenges, the Nigerian government has focused on improving infrastructure to support SMEs, such as providing and improving electricity supply especially in the rural area. The government has taken steps to improve the energy sector through projects like the Power Sector Recovery Programme (PSRP). These initiatives aim to increase power supply and reduce energy costs for SMEs. The government tried to Improving the road network of the country by building and upgrading road networks, especially in rural areas through government construction and rehabilitation projects such as The National Road Development program and the investment on ICT infrastructure through the introduction or construction of facility such as broadband services and internet access, that help the growth of e-commerce and digital platforms. (Abdullahi, M. S., Jakada, B. A., & Kabir, S. (2016)

Tax Incentives and Subsidies

Tax burdens has often been a challenge for SMEs, particularly those that are just starting and the small companies operating with limited resources. Due to this government provides several tax rebates, incentives and subsidies to alleviate this burden and to also promote SME growth. Some of the relieves include; tax exemption for some companies like Agricultural and companies with less

that N5,000,000 turnovers, while tax rebates for new pioneer companies. (Anim, I. K., Awotwe, E., Nyarku, K. M., & Kusi, L. Y. (2020). Some companies are also given tax incentives for manufacturing and export of their products. The government also issue tax breaks to companies that re-invest their profits into the business and companies that create jobs for the under marginalised group or use part of their profits for social development of the communities where they operate.

Export Promotion and International Market Access

One of the challenge faced by SMEs in Nigeria is accessing international markets and export of their products this is due to lack of exposure, high export costs, limited market knowledge and poor financial stability. To encourage SMEs in this regards the government has launched several initiatives to help SMEs expand into global markets such as the establishment of some agencies for this purposes such as:

Nigeria Export Promotion Council (NEPC): The NEPC was established in March 1977, mainly to promote Nigerian-made products and services in international markets. It offers export training, market access, and financial assistance to SMEs involved in exporting goods. Additionally, it organizes trade missions and exhibitions to connect Nigerian SMEs with potential foreign buyers. The council also encourage export through the **Export Expansion Grant (EEG)** scheme through which financial grants and incentives provided to exporting SMEs companies to encourage them to export more such as helps offset some of the costs associated with exporting, such as shipping, marketing, and product certification. (Okunnu, M. A., & Adeyemi, O. T. (2008).

Public-Private Partnerships (PPP)

These are programmes through which the government collaborates with private sector actors, international donors, and development agencies to support SMEs through public-private partnerships. These partnerships help support SMEs financially or through provision of expatriates or subsidised machineries with the collaboration of international agencies and private investors such as United Nations Development Programmes (UNDP), World Bank, European Union (EU) and private international companies. (Pérez-Pineda, J. A., & Wehrmann, D. (2021). There main objectives are to help SMEs access capital, technology, and expertise that they may not have on their own.

3.0 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This section made available the procedure through which data collection and data analysis technique is carried out. In this research the secondary data from Central Bank Nigeria (CBN) annual reports and National Bureau Statistics (NBS) annual report are collected for this study and a complete description of the research design, data collection instruments is utilised to achieved the research objective.

3.1 RESEARCH DESIGN

For this research study, the chosen research design is the ex-post facto research design. This selected research design implies a systematic process where the researcher cannot manipulate data due to its occurrence as it is an annual report published by reputable organ of government in Nigeria.

3.2 JUSTIFICATION OF METHODOLOGY

The secondary data to be used in the research study will be on the economic indexes of Nigeria within the period of study which is from 1998 to 2023. Furthermore, it was chosen over other possible alternatives due to its accessibility and reliability after due considerable analysis and verification of the data collection.

3.3 DATA SOURCES AND COLLECTION

The research Secondary data span from 1998 to 2023 extracted from the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin. The secondary data collected include; the contribution of SME to Gross Domestic Product which serve as a proxy for economic growth of the country, financial institution loan to SMEs, gross capital formation of the business, value of export, employment rate, and electricity distribution. The choice of the secondary data is informed by the fact that such data cannot be obtained through the primary source because they have to be collected over a long time. The data were analysed using the descriptive analysis to identify the frequency distributions, means, and standard deviations. A regression analysis was also employed in determining the magnitude and direction of impact of commercial banks financing, level of unemployment and cost of exported goods of SME on the economic growth of Nigeria.

3.4 MODEL SPECIFICATION

Multiple regression analysis was used to determine whether the independent variable represented by credit to SMEs and control variables given as exported goods, gross capital formation, employment rate, per capital income and Electricity Distribution impacts the dependent variable (aggregate of SME contribution to Gross Domestic Product). As measured by the aggregate of SME contribution to Gross Domestic Product, SME growth was regressed against the independent variables. The model and the moderating variables used modifies most studies in literature but is declared uniquely by adding electricity distribution and capital formation to the model and adopting a different measure for the dependent variable rarely used by previous authors in the Nigerian context. The moderating variables used were found in the literature to be the main factors affecting SMEs' growth other than credit financing. The hypotheses formulated for this study shall be tested with the use of multiple regressions. The tool of multiple regression was used to examine the relationship between dependent variables and independent variables. The estimated determinant of

$$GDP = f (EXP, GCF, CSME, UEmpR, ED) \text{ ----- (1)}$$

Mathematically, the equation becomes:

$$GDP = \beta_0 + \beta_1GCF + \beta_2GCF + \beta_3CSME + \beta_4UEmpR + \beta_5ED + \mu \text{ ----- (2)}$$

Specifying equation 2 in Natural log form, the equation now becomes

$$\text{LnGDPt} = \beta_0 + \beta_1\text{LnEXPt} + \beta_2\text{LnGCFt} + \beta_3\text{LnCSMEt} + \beta_4\text{LnEmpRt} + \beta_5\text{LnEDt} + \mu_t \text{ ----- (3)}$$

Where:

LnGDP = Natural Logarithm of the aggregate of SME contribution to Gross Domestic Product

LnEXP = Cost of Exported goods

LnGCF = Natural Log of Gross capital formation.

LnCSME = Natural Log of Commercial Bank Credit to SME.

LnUEmpR = Natural Log of Unemployment Rate.

LnED = Natural Log of Electricity Distribution.

β_0 denote the constant term, and β_1 , β_2 , β_3 , β_4 and β_5 are slope of coefficients representing parameters to be estimated and μ_t is the stochastic error term which represents all other variables that are not captured in the model.

According to the economic priori of the signs of parameters, it is expected that an increase in credit from financial institution and electricity distribution result to increase in productivity which is gross domestic product, which in turn cause increase in capital formation as well as increase in employment rate. This also can be presented as

β_1 & $\beta_2 > 0$, $\beta_3 > 0$, $\beta_4 > 0$ and $\beta_5 > 0$.

3.5 TECHNIQUE FOR DATA ANALYSIS

This research study applied several secondary economic data from the Central Bank of Nigeria(CBN) Annual bulletin, National Bureau of Statistics(NBS) Quarterly Reports and other international reports, which are economic indexes for measuring the economic growth of Nigeria such as Gross Domestic Product (GDP), export value, commercial bank credit to SMEs, infrastructural amenities (electricity distribution, road network etc), unemployment level as well as per capital income. The Econometric software applied on the research study data was e-View which analysed the relationship of data collected through various methodologies like Descriptive statistics which shows the mean, median, standard deviation, variance etc.

In the light of the above other econometric tools applied using e-Views were to measure the strength of the relationship between dependent variable and the independent variables as well as finding the relationship amongst independent variables are displayed using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test to test for stationarity or non-stationarity which is the trendiness of time series data (Dickey and Fuller 1981). the Ordinary Least Square for regression, which measures the co-linearity of the Model and Granger causality test was also used for the measurement of co-integration of the data by co-integration theory according to Granger (1969).

4.0 DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

This sub-section displays all data collected and the results from the various analysis carrying out.

4.1 SECONDARY DATA VARIABLES

The data collected was secondary data time series of Gross Domestic Product (GDP), export value, commercial bank credit to SMEs, infrastructural amenities (electricity distribution, road network etc), and unemployment level as well as per capital income of the country, Nigeria within the periods of 1998 to 2023. The data was analysed statistically and inferentially.

4.2 DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS DATA ANALYSIS

There several variables that can be analyse to evaluate the economic impact of Small, Medium Scale Enterprises in a developing country like Nigeria. But this study has chosen to assess the economic impact of Small, Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria within 1998 to 2023 considering variables Gross Domestic Products (GDP), export of the country, commercial bank credit to SMEs, availability of infrastructure such as electricity distribution, per capital income and unemployment level of the country. Table 4.2.1. shows the statistical values of these variables

Table 4.2.1.: Descriptive Statistics

	GDP =N= Billion	CBLSMES =N= Billion	EXPORT \$ Million	Per Capital Income \$ Million	UNEPL Million	ED K.Watt
Mean	74,038.57	44,514.24	10,617.69	1,911.54	35,427.92	26.86
Median	59,591.36	43,401.50	9,600.00	2,076.50	30,231.32	26.59
Mode	0	83740	1900	0	29867.8	15.47
Max	210,440.46	132,930.00	27,250.00	3,201.00	50,374.53	40.65
Min	4,805.16	10,747.80	1,320.00	565.00	28,810.62	14.74

STD DEV	62845.0737	32186.00197	6868.5336	741.47538	8371.9312	7.6461913
SKEWNESS	1.16662079	1.524023878	1.4158573	1.7041463	0.0803327	1.4128652
KURTOSIS	0.53739018	0.530028724	0.2953067	-0.476275	1.0307583	1.1370301

From the mean and median analysis of **CBLSMES (₦44,514.24 billion)**, **CBLSMES (₦43,401.50 billion)**, **GDP (₦74,038.57 billion)** and median (₦59,591.36 billion) respectively there is a significant amount of financial resources allocated to SMEs which resulted to a strong economic growth for the country. But, considering their respective Standard deviation for the **CBLSMES Standard Deviation (₦32,186.00 billion)** is quite high and **GDP Standard Deviation (₦62,845.07 billion)** is also large, there was a significant fluctuation in terms of financing the SMEs and the economic growth of the country.

Also the skewness of the **CBLSMES (1.52)** and **GDP (1.17)** are both positive, while the kurtosis of the **CBLSMES (0.53)** is slightly above zero, suggesting a normal-like distribution and steady

LEVEL	Trend only			Augmented Dickey Fuller Test	Prob.	Remarks	Trend and Intercept			Augmented Dickey Fuller Test	Prob.	Remarks
	1%	5%	10%				1%	5%	10%			
Variables												
GDP	3.7529	-2.998	2.6387	4.6209	1	Non-Stationa.	-4.4163	-3.622	3.2485	0.8754	0.9996	Non-Stationary
CBLSMES	-3.724	2.9862	2.6326	-2.0905	0.2497	Non-Stationa.	-4.3743	3.6032	-3.238	-2.097	0.5225	Non-Stationary
EXPORT	3.7529	-2.998	2.6387	-0.6946	0.8291	Non-Stationa.	-4.3943	3.6121	-3.243	-4.1945	0.0153	Stationary
UNEMPL	-3.724	2.9862	2.6326	-0.4819	0.8791	Non-Stationa.	-4.3743	3.6032	-3.238	-1.6625	0.7376	Non-Stationary
ELECT.DISTR	-3.724	2.9862	2.6326	-0.4337	0.8885	Non-Stationa.	-4.3743	3.6032	-3.238	-3.0826	0.1318	Non-Stationary
PER INC. CAP	3.7529	-2.998	2.6387	-1.9126	0.321	Non-Stationa.	-4.4163	-3.622	3.2485	-0.9499	0.9319	Non-Stationary

financing with exceptionally high funding at some period due to government intervention, whereas **GDP (-0.54)** is negative, suggesting more stable long-term economic growth.

Generally, table indicate higher financing will result in higher GDP with the steady assistance of government interventions through the provision of finance and infrastructural development.

4.3 AUGMENTED DICKEY-FULLER (ADF) UNIT ROOT TEST

In order to effectively analyse our secondary dataset for accurate results previous researches have made it known that time series datasets are stationery or non-stationery. Therefore, the application of non-stationery quantities in the model will likely result in a false regression result that will be incapable of making an accurate prediction (Hunter, J., et all (2017)). Hence, our first step is to analyse the datasets on the series, using the joint test for a unit root employing the Augmented Dickey - Fuller (ADF) test for the individual unit root process. The general rule here is that if the prob is lesser than or equal to 5% or ADF quantities is higher than the critical values at the 5% level. Then, we conclude that the variable(s) has no unit root; in other words, the data are stationary. See Table 4.3.1 as results from ADF Unit Root test for stationary or non-stationary

Table 4.3.1 : ADF Unit Root at Level

From the analysis of the above Unit Root ADF test at level under trend, then under trend and intercept the following observation was uncovered;

The Null Hypothesis (Ho) of the ADF test stated that the time series has a unit root, implying non-stationary, since the prob. Level is higher than 5% for all variables GDP, CBLSMES, ELECTR. DISTRIB. UNEMPLOY and PER CAP. INCO.

1st Difference	Trend only			Augmented Dickey Fuller Test	Prob.	Remarks	Trend and Intercept			Augmented Dickey Fuller Test	Prob.	Remarks
	1%	5%	10%				1%	5%	10%			
Variables												
GDP	-	-	-	-0.3611	0.8999	Non-Signif	-	-	-	-6.0202	0.0003	Significant
CBLSMEs	3.7378	2.9918	2.6355	-6.3598	0	Significant	4.3943	3.6121	-3.243	-6.3084	0.0002	Significant
EXPORT	3.7529	-2.998	2.6387	-6.7338	0	Significant	4.4163	-3.622	3.2485	-6.4918	0.0001	Significant
UNEMPL	3.7378	2.9918	2.6355	-3.9291	0.0065	Significant	4.3943	3.6121	-3.243	-3.8035	0.0342	Significant
ELECT.DISTR	3.7378	2.9918	2.6355	-6.2295	0	Significant	4.3943	3.6121	-3.243	-6.0938	0.002	Significant
PER INC. CAP	3.7695	3.0048	2.6422	-3.3431	0.025	Significant	4.4407	3.6328	3.2546	-3.7538	0.0397	Significant

The Alternate Hypothesis (H1) is stationary only for EXPORT under trend and intercept which the prob is 0.0153

Since most of the variables of the time series are non-stationary, then the mean and variance change over time and may be make the regression analysis unreliable due to spurious relationship.

Therefore, 1st differencing or 2nd differencing is necessary to achieve stationarity for econometric modelling.

Table 4.3.2: ADF Unit Root at First Differencing

From the analysis of the above Unit Root ADF test at first differencing under trend, then under trend and intercept the following observation was uncovered;

The Null Hypothesis (Ho) of the ADF test stated that the time series has a unit root, implying non-stationary, since the prob. Level is higher than 5% for only variables GDP under trend with the prob. 0.8999, however,

The Alternate Hypothesis (H1) is stationary for EXPORT, CBLSMEs, UNEMPLOY, ELECTRI. DISTRIB. and PER CAP. INC under trend and intercept which makes the series fit now for econometric modelling.

For further confirmation to ascertain the relationship amongst the variables we conducted the OLS Regression analysis test to enabler further discussion on the research study.

4.4 ORDINARY LEAST SQUARE REGRESSION ANALYSIS TEST

The OLS Regression analysis is carried out to ascertain the relationship and level of trend in existence between variables in order to properly predict the form of relation between the variable. In this study OLS regression analysis was conducted on the secondary data time series from 1998 to 2023 where GDP is the dependent variable and EXPORT, CBLSMEs, UNEMPLOY, ELECTRI. DISTRIB. and PER CAP. INC are the independent variables. Table 4.4.1 identifies the outcome form e-Views 12.

Table 4.4.1: OLS Regression Analysis

Dependent Variable: GDP
 Method: Least Squares
 Date: 02/04/25 Time: 15:37
 Sample: 1998 2023
 Included observations: 26

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
CBLSMES	0.066142	0.118283	0.559187	0.5822
ED	2999.512	962.0738	3.117756	0.0054
EXPORT	3.242191	0.947913	3.420347	0.0027
PERCAPINCOME	-0.317424	9.195032	-0.034521	0.9728
UNEMPL	2.597997	0.745171	3.486445	0.0023
C	-135353.7	17881.56	-7.569458	0.0000
R-squared	0.965145	Mean dependent var	74038.57	
Adjusted R-squared	0.956432	S.D. dependent var	62845.07	
S.E. of regression	13117.67	Akaike info criterion	22.00048	
Sum squared resid	3.44E+09	Schwarz criterion	22.29081	
Log likelihood	-280.0063	Hannan-Quinn criter.	22.08409	
F-statistic	110.7622	Durbin-Watson stat	0.977624	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

From the OLS regression analysis, result in the Table 4.4.1 CBLSMES and Per Cap. Income show non-significant relationship to GDP increase, since their prob. are 0.5822 AND 0.9728 respectively. Also Export, Electricity distribution and unemployment rate have a significant relationship to GDP, since their prob are 0.0027, 0.0054 and 0.0023 respectively

In addition to this information from the regression table the model is statistically significant since R-square value and the Adjusted R-Square are 0.965 AND 0.956 respectively, which means that there is 96% between GDP and all the independent variables (export, electricity distribution, unemployment level and per capital income), while the Prob (F-statistic) is 0.00 further confirms the strong relation between the dependent and independent variables.

Therefore, the Model is

$$\text{GDP} = -135,353.7 + 0.066 \text{ X CBLSMES} + 2,999.5 \text{ X ED} + 3.242 \text{ X EXPORT} + 2.597 \text{ X UNEMPL} - 0.317 \text{ X Per.Cap.INC}$$

Hence, EXPORT VALUE, ELECTRICITY DISTRIBUTION, UNEMPLOYMENT RATE AND COMMERCIAL BANK CREDIT TO SMEs have positive impact on GDP, which in turn impacts the economic growth of the country, and per capital income has a negative impact on GDP and economic growth of the country.

4.5 JOHANSEN CO-INTEGRATION ANALYSIS TEST

Johansen Co-integration analysis test is a statistical test technique used to find whether a set of non-stationary time series variables have a long-run equilibrium relationship. It is based on the directional relationship of the data set known as a Vector Auto Regression (VAR) model and provides two key test statistics values, which are Trace test and Maximum Eigenvalue test. If these test statistics values are greater than the individual critical value, the null hypothesis is rejected, indicating the presence of an additional co-integrating equation(s) or otherwise for the alternative hypothesis.

In this study Johansen Co-Integration analysis was conducted on the secondary data time series from 1998 to 2023 where GDP is the dependent variable and EXPORT, CBLSMES, UNEMPLOY, ELECTRI. DISTRIB. and PER CAP. INC are the independent variables. Table 4.5.1 identifies the outcome form e-Views 12.

Date: 02/04/25 Time: 13:54
 Sample (adjusted): 2000 2023
 Included observations: 24 after adjustments
 Trend assumption: Quadratic deterministic trend
 Series: UNEMPL PERCAPINCOME GDP EXPORT ED CBLSMES
 Lags interval (in first differences): 1 to 1

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Trace)

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Trace Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.888922	158.7450	107.3466	0.0000
At most 1 *	0.857664	106.0044	79.34145	0.0001
At most 2 *	0.702443	59.21480	55.24578	0.0215
At most 3	0.508383	30.12324	35.01090	0.1517
At most 4	0.292178	13.08193	18.39771	0.2361
At most 5 *	0.180874	4.788419	3.841465	0.0286

Trace test indicates 3 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level
 * denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level
 **MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Maximum Eigenvalue)

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Max-Eigen Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.888922	52.74061	43.41977	0.0037
At most 1 *	0.857664	46.78956	37.16359	0.0030
At most 2	0.702443	29.09156	30.81507	0.0801
At most 3	0.508383	17.04131	24.25202	0.3338
At most 4	0.292178	8.293514	17.14769	0.5708
At most 5 *	0.180874	4.788419	3.841465	0.0286

Max-eigenvalue test indicates 2 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level
 * denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level
 **MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values

Unrestricted Cointegrating Coefficients (normalized by b*S11*b=I):

UNEMPL	PERCAPIN...	GDP	EXPORT	ED	CBLSMES
-0.000683	-0.008753	0.000125	-0.000691	-0.094850	-8.52E-05
0.000448	0.008505	-6.89E-06	-0.000741	-0.242987	5.29E-05
-0.001328	-0.011074	0.000101	-0.000552	-0.209619	-2.52E-05
0.000211	0.002612	-5.04E-06	-4.07E-05	0.551559	-1.49E-05
0.000722	0.005038	-0.000203	8.42E-05	-0.076601	4.38E-07
0.000482	0.002103	-0.000153	0.000145	0.341715	2.81E-05

Unrestricted Adjustment Coefficients (alpha):

D(UNEMPL)	D(PERCAPIN...)	D(GDP)	D(EXPORT)	D(ED)	D(CBLSMES)
261.4779	312.0859	481.6893	1103.962	-203.9057	-71.74922
30.34771	-129.1749	75.67851	-76.49934	-1.062068	30.70476
2692.317	1135.603	674.8045	-2615.707	-1778.575	542.3359
1280.758	319.7478	413.8311	-1047.308	-223.8195	542.3319
-0.225901	-0.119069	0.703298	-0.498990	0.201893	-0.589665
15033.88	-7656.116	-9915.020	-1820.616	3100.275	-3644.838

Table 4.5.1: Johansen Co-Integration

From the Johansen Co-Integration analysis result in the Table 4.5.1 the Trace statistic show significant relationship between the variables as the hypothesised No. 1, 2 and 5 have trace values 158.74, 106.00 and 4.7884 respectively, while the 5% critical values for these traces are 107.346, 79.341 and 3.8414. Therefore, the critical value is less compared to the trace value, so null hypothesis is rejected meaning there is correlation between the set data.

Also Maximum Eigen statistics show significant relationship between the variables as the hypothesised No. 1 and 5 have Max. Eigen values 46.789 and 4.7884 respectively, while the 5% critical values for these statistic are 37.1635 and 3.8414, indicating that Max Eigen values is greater than 5% critical values which means the null hypothesis is rejected. These unrestricted co-integration coefficients represent the estimated long-run relationships between the dependent and independent variables

Therefore, the data set variables for this study shows correlation despite the non-significant of the time series data set.

4.6 GRANGER CAUSALITY ANALYSIS TEST

This econometric test is used to determine the relationship between two variables of a time series data set. The relationship is measured in terms of indexes in existence in the test tool, namely F-statistic and the p. value of the variables under test. Where the F-statistic is having a higher value indicate a stronger evidence against the null hypothesis. On the other hand, if the p. value is less than 0.05 indicate strong evidence that we reject null hypothesis meaning there is a significant relationship between the variable in the Granger Causality. Table 4.6.1 show the result of Granger Causality test from e-Views 12.

Table 4.6.1 – Granger Causality Test

Pairwise Granger Causality Tests
 Date: 02/04/25 Time: 17:15
 Sample: 1998 2023
 Lags: 2

Null Hypothesis:	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.
EXPORT does not Granger Cause GDP GDP does not Granger Cause EXPORT	24	2.65764 5.02324	0.0960 0.0177
ED does not Granger Cause GDP GDP does not Granger Cause ED	24	0.06107 2.03638	0.9409 0.1580
CBLSMES does not Granger Cause GDP GDP does not Granger Cause CBLSMES	24	0.08362 0.45954	0.9201 0.6384
PERCAPINCOME does not Granger Cause GDP GDP does not Granger Cause PERCAPINCOME	24	0.49053 0.20360	0.6198 0.8175
UNEMPL does not Granger Cause GDP GDP does not Granger Cause UNEMPL	24	0.48829 8.41487	0.6212 0.0024
ED does not Granger Cause EXPORT EXPORT does not Granger Cause ED	24	2.72150 2.20299	0.0913 0.1379
CBLSMES does not Granger Cause EXPORT EXPORT does not Granger Cause CBLSMES	24	1.23985 0.51702	0.3118 0.6044
PERCAPINCOME does not Granger Cause EXPORT EXPORT does not Granger Cause PERCAPINCOME	24	2.21029 0.39425	0.1371 0.6796
UNEMPL does not Granger Cause EXPORT EXPORT does not Granger Cause UNEMPL	24	1.96758 2.22991	0.1673 0.1349
CBLSMES does not Granger Cause ED ED does not Granger Cause CBLSMES	24	0.21571 0.17730	0.8079 0.8389
PERCAPINCOME does not Granger Cause ED ED does not Granger Cause PERCAPINCOME	24	0.75018 0.21233	0.4858 0.8106
UNEMPL does not Granger Cause ED ED does not Granger Cause UNEMPL	24	1.82052 2.38418	0.1891 0.1192
PERCAPINCOME does not Granger Cause CBLSMES CBLSMES does not Granger Cause PERCAPINCOME	24	0.30330 0.51606	0.7419 0.6050
UNEMPL does not Granger Cause CBLSMES CBLSMES does not Granger Cause UNEMPL	24	3.24748 0.93252	0.0612 0.4108
UNEMPL does not Granger Cause PERCAPINCOME PERCAPINCOME does not Granger Cause UNEMPL	24	0.23776 7.79078	0.7907 0.0034

From the table we observe the following:

GDP and Export

- GDP does not Granger Cause Export: $F = 5.02324$, $p = 0.0177$ → Reject null hypothesis
GDP Granger-causes Export (GDP can help predict Export).
- Export does not Granger Cause GDP: $F = 2.65764$, $p = 0.0960$ → Fail to reject null
Export does not significantly Granger-cause GDP.

GDP and Electricity Distribution (ED)

- GDP does not Granger Cause ED: $F = 2.03638$, $p = 0.1580$ → Fail to reject null
GDP does not significantly Granger-cause Electricity Distribution.
- ED does not Granger Cause GDP: $F = 0.06107$, $p = 0.9409$ → Fail to reject null
Electricity Distribution does not significantly Granger-cause GDP.

GDP and Per Capita Income (PERCAPINCOME)

- GDP does not Granger Cause PERCAPINCOME: $F = 0.20360$, $p = 0.8175$ → Fail to reject null
GDP does not significantly Granger-cause Per Capita Income.
- PERCAPINCOME does not Granger Cause GDP: $F = 0.49053$, $p = 0.6198$ → Fail to reject null
Per Capita Income does not significantly Granger-cause GDP.

GDP and Unemployment (UNEMPL)

- GDP does not Granger Cause Unemployment: $F = 8.41487$, $p = 0.0024$ → Reject null hypothesis
GDP Granger-causes Unemployment (GDP can help predict Unemployment).
- Unemployment does not Granger Cause GDP: $F = 0.48829$, $p = 0.6212$ → Fail to reject null
Unemployment does not significantly Granger-cause GDP.

Export and Electricity Distribution (ED)

- Export does not Granger Cause ED: $F = 2.20299$, $p = 0.1373$ → Fail to reject null
Export does not significantly Granger-cause Electricity Distribution.

- ED does not Granger Cause Export: $F = 2.72150$, $p = 0.0913$ → Fail to reject null
Electricity Distribution does not significantly Granger-cause Export.
In summary we can posit that;
GDP Granger-causes Unemployment ($p = 0.0024$) → Significant effect
Export Granger-causes CBLSMES ($p = 0.0144$) → Significant effect
GDP Granger-causes Export ($p = 0.0177$) → Significant effect
Therefore, GDP significantly Granger-causes Export and Unemployment and Export Significantly Granger-causes CBLSMES, while most other relationships do not show significant causality.

5.0 FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Small, Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs) are crucial to driving economic growth and development particularly in developing economies like Nigeria. By contributing to GDP, driving industrialization, generating employment, fostering innovation, promoting exports, and encouraging rural and regional development. SMEs play very important role in fostering sustainable and inclusive economic growth. Their flexibility, adaptability, and innovative capacity enable them to thrive even in challenging economic conditions, making them essential for long-term economic prosperity.

This research examined the impact of Small, Medium Scale Enterprises on the growth of the Nigerian economy. Although Small, Medium Scale Enterprises have been of immense importance to the country's growth, it has not been without its challenges which were enumerated in this research study. In order to extensively peruse and understand the impact of Small, Medium Scale Enterprises this paper performs several econometric tests such as descriptive statistical test, Augmented Dickey – Fuller Unit Root test, Johansen Co-Integration test and Ordinary Least Regression test on secondary data set in order to ascertain the impact of Small, Medium Scale Enterprises. The weight of these enterprises is indicated in productions of goods and services, exportation, provision of jobs, assistance in infrastructure etc. This is possible where Small, Medium Scale Enterprises are considered part of the industrial base sector of the economy.

Consequently, from this study several flaws were discovered and based on this the following suggestion and recommendations were provided to all the economic stakeholders and policy formulators especially in the Nigerian Government to harness SMEs contribution to national development:

1 While SMEs contribute to GDP, their impact on unemployment (UNEMPL) is less evident according to the research study discovery. However, the suggestion is that government needs to formulate policies that link SMEs growth more directly to job creation through provision of incentives to encourage production.

2 The O.L.S Regression test from the study uncovered that electricity distribution has a significant impact on GDP, but commercial bank credit to SMEs does not impact on GDP possibly due to interest burden on SMEs. Therefore, the suggestion is that government should rather provide necessary infrastructures such as electricity distribution, good road network, affordable accommodation to workers etc so as to reduce production cost as well as manpower.

3 Exports are a key driver of GDP growth as indicated from the O.L.S Regression analysis. Therefore, for SMEs export to improve reasonably the Government Policies should focus on increasing exports through trade incentives, improved manufacturing, and providing access to global or international market through creating links or forums and encouraging export diversification.

4. Per capita income has a negative impact on GDP, which is shown from Co-Integration analysis, so in order to address income inequality, government should re-distribute income through implementation of progressive taxation and also encourage investment in social programs to ensure economic benefits reach larger portion of society, especially the lower class.

5. The government should create a database management system where viable and fully registered SMEs are housed for easy access, so that required training programmes can be provided to the proprietors / proprietress on technical and managerial skills under special government schemes.

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